

Evaluation Of Anti-Thyroid Potentials Of *Pimpinella anisum* Fruit Ethanolic Extract Against Thyroxine Induced Hyperthyroidism Rats

M. Sania Tahseen¹, Sura Suman^{*2}

¹Dept. of Pharmacology, Creative Educational Society's College of Pharmacy, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

²Dept. of Pharmacology, Creative Educational Society's College of Pharmacy, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh.

ABSTRACT

Hyperthyroidism is an extensive endocrine disorder exemplified by the excessive synthesis and secretion of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) by the thyroid gland, leading to a hypermetabolic clinical state known as thyrotoxicosis. Approximately 0.2% to 1.3% of the global population is impacting with a higher incidence in women and a distinct occurrence in older adults. The most common etiology is Graves' disease, followed by toxic nodular goiter and toxic adenoma. This has created flourishing interest in safe, plant-based substitute with multifunctional benefits. *Pimpinella anisum* (also known as Anise or aniseed) is a well-authenticated medicinal plant in Ayurveda and traditional medicine, valued for its diverse therapeutic properties. Hyperthyroidism was induced in experimental rats by administering thyroxine (600µg/kg/ml) orally for 14 days. Hyperthyroid wistar rats weighing 150-200gm were treated with oral doses of 100mg/kg, 200mg/kg, and 400mg/kg of *Pimpinella anisum* ethanolic extract for a period of 28 days. Methimazole (0.04%w/v) for 28 days, served as standard. In this study, Body weight, food and water intake were decreased, serum levels of T₃, T₄, total cholesterol, LDL, HDL are elevated and VLDL, and triglyceride levels were diminished in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats, concurrent administration of methimazole (0.04%w/v) and *Pimpinella anisum* fruits ethanolic extract with distinct doses reversed these changes in hyperthyroidism rats' dose dependently.

Keywords: Methimazole, *Pimpinella anisum*, Thyroxine, T₃, T₄, TSH.

INTRODUCTION

Hyperthyroidism is an extensive endocrine disorder exemplified by the excessive synthesis and secretion of thyroid hormones (T₃ and T₄) by the thyroid gland, leading to a hypermetabolic clinical state known as thyrotoxicosis. Approximately 0.2% to 1.3% of the global population is impacting with a higher incidence in women and a distinct occurrence in older adults. The most common etiology is Graves' disease, followed by toxic nodular goiter and toxic adenoma¹. While the widely used conventional antithyroid drugs such as methimazole (MMI), carbimazole (CMZ), and propylthiouracil (PTU). These agents are crucial for managing Graves' disease and preparing patients for surgery or radioiodine, they often present significant limitations including high relapse rates (30-70%), side effects, and long treatment durations². These limitations have prompted the exploration of

alternative therapies, particularly those derived from natural sources. *Pimpinella anisum* widely known anise and aniseed, widely used medicinal plant in food and vernacular treatments, due to the existence of the rich phytoconstituents. The literature revealed that, in Southern areas (i.e. Tan-Tan), *Pimpinella anisum* is used in phytotherapy mainly in urinary tract infections principally against pyelonephritis and cystitis, respiratory disorders, as carminative, digestive treatments 3-6

Phytochemicals have been shown to have either beneficial or detrimental effects on thyroid function. Some flavonoids have been reported to affect the expression and the activity of several thyroid-related enzymes and proteins, the beneficial effects of some plant-derived compounds, such as myricetin, quercetin, apigenin, rutin, genistein, and curcumin, and their possible role as adjuvants for the treatment

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of thyroid disorders have been described⁷. By considering the above the present study was designed to demonstrate the antithyroid activity of *Pimpinella anisum* fruits ethanolic extract.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Wistar albino male rats (150-200g) were maintained for 7 days in the animal house of Creative Educational Society's college of Pharmacy, Kurnool under standard temperature conditions ($24^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) with 60% relative humidity and illuminated 12/24 h⁸. The animals were allowed to acclimatize to laboratory conditions 48 h before the start of the experiment. 6 rats / group were used in all sets of experiments. The animals were allowed free access to drinking water and rat feed⁹. All the protocols Experimental Animals were approved by IAEC with the approval number: IAEC/CESCOP/2025-02-07

Preparation of Extract:

The *Pimpinella anisum* fruits were collected from the local market of Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh, India and authenticated by Prof. Dr. R.Vinolya Kumari, Associate Professor of Botany & HOD, Department of Botany, Silver Jubilee Govt. College, Cluster University, Kurnool. The fruits were dried in shade and powdered to coarse for further process. Powdered fruits of *Pimpinella anisum* was sieved (0.2 mm) then powder was crammed in a thimble and subjected to extraction by using individual solvents using Soxhlet apparatus. Solvents are selected by increasing polarity namely petroleum ether, diethyl ether, chloroform, ethanol and water were used. The crude *Pimpinella anisum* material was extracted in the ratio of (1:3) i.e. for one part of the powder material three parts of solvent. Extraction process was performed until to get colorless solvent. The evaporated extract was stored in a desiccator.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis:

The extract was subjected to various qualitative tests to determine the presence of various phytoconstituents using reported methods. Alkaloids were tested by Dragendorff, Wagner and Mayer tests, Hagner's test while phenolic and flavonoid were tested by ferric chloride, Shinoda and lead acetate test.

Salkowski test was used for the detection of triterpenoid and steroidal saponins. Terpenoids and steroids were detected by vanillin sulphuric acid and Liebermann–Burchard tests. Tannins were tested by ferric chloride test, catechin test and chlorogenic acid test. Glycosides were tested by Keller–Killani test, Legal test, Baljet test and foam test¹⁰.

Acute Toxicity studies:

Acute toxicity studies have been carried out according to OECD-423 guidelines to determine the non-lethal dose¹¹. The test procedure was carried out using wistar albino rats with the starting dose of 5mg/kg, body weight and continued upto the dose range of 2000mg/kg, body weight¹².

Antithyroid activity:

Experimental design:

Animals were divided into six groups, each consisting of six rats. The control group rats were given distilled water 5 ml/kg (p.o.). The other groups of animals were administered with thyroxine (600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) (p.o.) for 14 days to induce hyperthyroidism. After 14 days of the administration, all the animals were screened for biochemical markers like triiodothyronine(T3), total thyroxine(T4), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), and for the next 14 days, rats were administered with different treatments as follows.

Treatment design¹³:

Group I: Normal diet (control) (28 days with vehicle)

Group-II: Hyperthyroid-induced animals (thyroxine 600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{ml}$) for 14 days + 14 days vehicle.

Group-III: Hyperthyroid-induced animals treated with standard drug (Methimazole 0.04% w/v) for 28 days. (14 days Thyroxine +14 days Methimazole)

Group-IV: Hyperthyroid-induced animals treated with *Pimpinella anisum* fruits ethanolic extract (100mg/kg) for 28 days. (14 days Thyroxine +14 days low dose)

Group-V: Hyperthyroid-induced animals treated with Pimpinella anisum fruits ethanolic extract (200mg/kg) for 28 days. (14 days Thyroxine +14 days medium dose)

Group-VI Hyperthyroid-induced animals treated with Pimpinella anisum fruits ethanolic extract (400mg/kg) for 28 days. (14 days Thyroxine +14 days high dose)

Evaluation of Parameters:

Body and Organ Weights:

Body weights of each rat were measured with a weekly interval using automatic electronic balance. At the last day of the experimental procedure, the weight of liver, left thyroid gland, was measured at g levels (absolute weights), and to reduce the differences from individual body weights, the relative weight (% of g or mg/g body weight) was calculated as $\text{Relative Weight} = \{\text{Absolute Organ weight (g or mg)} \div \text{Body weight at sacrifice (g)}\} \times 1009$

Measurement of Food and water intake:

All the group of animals were observed food consumption and water intake was measured at the initiation of experiment and once in 14 days during the treatment period for 28 days¹⁰

Estimation of Total Cholesterol, HDL, LDL and VLDL

Lipid irregularities may ascribe to the disabled thyroid capacity. Before the accessibility of serum thyroid hormone estimations, serum cholesterol level was utilized to help in the judgment of the thyroid issue. Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL, VLDL and triglycerides were determined. Following twenty-eight days of treatment with standard medication and Pimpinella anisum fruits ethanolic extract with three different doses (100mg/kg, 200mg/kg, and 400mg/kg) total cholesterol, HDL and LDL levels enhanced while VLDL and triglycerides diminished essentially and arrived at normal extent¹⁴.

Estimation of Serum Thyroid Hormones (T3, T4, & TSH).

Thyroxine (T4) treatment induced a significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in the serum T3 and T4 levels and a decrease in the serum TSH contents. In Methimazole 0.04% w/v administered group (G-III levels were significantly ($p < 0.001$) there was decrease in the serum T3 and T4 levels and increase the TSH levels when compared with normal group (G-II). In EEPA administered groups (G-IV and G-V), T3 and T4 levels were significantly ($p < 0.001$) decreased and increase in the TSH levels when compared with Disease control group (G-II). A prominent effect was observed in the high-dose extract-treated group compared to a low-dose treated group¹⁵.

Histopathological studies:

After the rats were sacrificed, the thyroid glands were collected, weighed, and stored in 10% formaldehyde solution before being sent for histopathological examination.

Statistical analysis:

The experimental results were expressed as the mean \pm SEM ($n=6$). Data was analyzed using ANOVA followed by the Dunnett test. P values of ≤ 0.05 and ≤ 0.01 were considered statistically significant. Data was processed using GraphPad Prism version

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preparation of plant extract:

The extraction of Pimpinella Anisum fruits using ethanol was prepared by using Soxhlet extraction method. The dried extract was weighed and kept in air closed containers. The percentage yield of ethanolic extract was found to be 48.6%.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis

Qualitative phytochemical studies were performed on extracts the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, steroids, tannins and phenolics. The grades of qualitative phytochemical studies indicates that the maximum number of chemical constituents were present in the ethanolic extract when compared to the other extracts and hence ethanol extract was selected for further pharmacological screening.

Table:1 Phytochemical analysis of Pimpinella anisum Fruits Ethanolic extract

Phytoconstituents	Methods	Results
Alkaloids	Dragondroffs test	+
	Mayers test	+
	Wagners test	+
Glycosides	Brontragaes test	+
Tannins	Ferric chloride test	+
Flavonoids	Shinoda test	+
Terpenoids	Liebermans test	-
Phenols	Ferric chloride test	+
Saponins	Foam test	-

“ + ” indicates presence

“ - ” indicates absence

Acute toxicity studies:

The purified and completely dried ethanolic extract of Pimpinella anisum fruit was subjected for the acute toxicity study to determine the lethal dose using Wistar albino mice in forced environment. Acute toxicity studies were performed according to the OECD 423 guidelines. The EEPA (2000mg/b.w) was administered by oral route to a group of rats using oral feeding needle (22 gauge). After treatment to rats were monitored for 14 days and it was observed that non changes in normal behavior, hence it was confirmed that the EEPA is virtually nontoxic in normal rats and fall under the sort of GHS category 5, according

to 2/20th dose (100mg/kg b.w), 1/10th of dose (200/kg b.w), 1/5th dose (400mg/kg b.w) from maximum safe dose was considered for further evaluation of pharmacological studies.

Effect of Pimpinella anisum Fruit ethanolic extract on thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism in rats**Effect on Body weight, & Organ Weights**

Table 2 and Graph 1 indicated rats treated with thyroxine decreases the body weight, and after treatment with methimazole and EEPA there is a restoration of body weights.

Table 2: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Body weights of thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

S. No	Animal Group	Body Weight (gm/kg)		
		0 Day	14 th Day	28 th Day
1	Group-I	139.7±4.63	159.2±3.71	166.2±3.73
2	Group-II	149.7±3.43	116.4±3.72	103.7±2.86
3	Group-III	154.5±2.14	136.8±2.31	141.5±3.43
4	Group-IV	142.7±3.75	129.2±3.84	134.5±2.77
5	Group-V	149.3±2.41	135.3±2.86	142.5±2.32
6	Group-VI	140.8±3.91	129.7±3.52	132.2±3.45

Graph 1: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Body weights of thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

Measurement of Food and Water Intake

initiation of experiment and once in 14 days during the treatment period.

All the group of animals were observed food consumption and water intake was measured at the

Table 3: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on food intake in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

S. No	Animal Group	Food Intake (gm)		
		0 Day	14 th Day	28 th Day
1	Group-I	21.85±2.46	24.36±2.48	23.74±2.69
2	Group-II	23.78±1.65	20.88±3.45	18.32±1.63
3	Group-III	20.75±2.87	15.58±1.68	19.51±2.69
4	Group-IV	22.65±1.88	18.74±2.75	20.48±3.65
5	Group-V	24.91±2.48	20.98±2.18	21.85±1.42
6	Group-VI	20.54±2.78	17.37±1.85	18.68±1.26

Graph 2: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on food intake in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

Table 3 and Graph 2 revealed rats treated with thyroxine decreases the food intake, and after treatment with methimazole and EEPA there is a reestablishment of food intake.

Table 4: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Water intake in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

S. No	Animal Group	Water Intake (ml)		
		0 Day	14 th Day	28 th Day
1	Group-I	10.45±1.45	12.85±3.68	11.65±1.75
2	Group-II	12.84±2.15	11.45±2.42	9.27±1.32
3	Group-III	11.41±1.33	10.24±1.94	12.35±1.57
4	Group-IV	10.22±2.48	9.32±3.14	11.45±2.55
5	Group-V	11.58±1.25	10.18±1.65	10.85±1.73
6	Group-VI	10.65±0.95	9.15±2.34	10.91±1.28

Graph 3: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on water intake in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

Table 4 and Graph 3 showed rats treated with thyroxine decreases the water intake, and after treatment with methimazole and EEPA there is a reestablishment of water intake.

Estimation of Total Cholesterol, HDL, LDL and VLDL

Lipid irregularities may ascribe to the disabled thyroid capacity. Before the accessibility of serum thyroid hormone estimations, serum cholesterol level was utilized to help in the judgment of the thyroid issue.

Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL, VLDL and triglycerides were determined. Following twenty-eight days of treatment with standard medication and Pimpinella anisum fruits ethanolic extract with three different doses (100mg/kg, 200mg/kg, and 400mg/kg) total cholesterol, HDL and LDL levels enhanced while VLDL and triglycerides diminished essentially and arrived at normal extent.

Table 5: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL and VLDL levels in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

S. No	Animal Group	Lipid Profile (mg/dl)				
		Total Cholesterol	HDL	LDL	VLDL	Triglycerides
1	Group-I	135.8±1.64	44.32±0.26	84.69±1.03	8.75±0.81	31.65±1.54
2	Group-II	93.5±2.46 ^{###}	21.85±1.31 ^{###}	58.74±0.45 ^{###}	13.68±0.75 ^{###}	45.21±2.87 ^{###}
3	Group-III	113.4±3.25 ^{***}	39.54±0.34 ^{***}	78.66±1.58 ^{***}	11.33±0.25 ^{***}	32.95±1.69 ^{***}
4	Group-IV	110.5±3.88 [*]	28.65±0.58 ^{**}	61.74±1.68 [*]	10.25±0.47 [*]	42.45±1.05 ^{**}
5	Group-V	112.5±1.43 ^{**}	32.73±0.24 ^{**}	65.84±2.84 ^{**}	9.38±0.39 ^{**}	39.48±2.45 ^{**}
6	Group-VI	119.2±2.63 ^{***}	35.48±1.36 ^{**}	75.48±1.25 ^{***}	8.95±0.73 ^{**}	34.87±1.48 ^{***}

Graph 4: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL and VLDL levels in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

Estimation of Serum Thyroid Hormones (T3, T4, & TSH).

Thyroxine (T4) treatment induced a significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in the serum T3 and T4 levels and a decrease in the serum TSH contents. In Methimazole 0.04% w/v administered group (G-III) levels were significantly ($p < 0.001$) there was decrease in the serum T3 and T4 levels and increase the TSH levels when compared with normal group (G-II). In EEPA administered groups (G-IV and G-V), T3 and T4 levels were significantly ($p < 0.001$) decreased and increase in the TSH levels when compared with Disease control group (G-II). A prominent effect was

observed in the high-dose extract-treated group compared to a low-dose treated group.

Table 6: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Serum Thyroid Hormone levels (T3, T4, & TSH) in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

Animal groups	T3(ng/ml)			T4(ng/ml)			TSH(μ g/ml)		
	0 day	14 th day	28 th day	0 day	14 th day	28 th day	0 day	14 th day	28 th day
Group-I	1.71 \pm 0.12	1.85 \pm 0.07	1.85 \pm 0.11	4.65 \pm 0.18	4.75 \pm 0.07	4.50 \pm 0.11	0.68 \pm 0.03	0.68 \pm 0.16	0.67 \pm 0.14
Group-II	1.82 \pm 0.07	4.46 \pm 0.18	4.85 \pm 0.09 ^{###}	5.28 \pm 0.47	9.61 \pm 0.15	9.96 \pm 0.17 ^{###}	0.75 \pm 0.05	0.21 \pm 0.04	0.23 \pm 0.15 ^{###}
Group-III	1.63 \pm 0.08	4.68 \pm 0.11	2.05 \pm 0.07 ^{**}	5.12 \pm 0.29	9.25 \pm 0.16	5.55 \pm 0.14 ^{**}	0.62 \pm 0.01	0.23 \pm 0.15	0.65 \pm 0.25 ^{**}
Group-IV	1.96 \pm 0.12	4.83 \pm 0.11	3.08 \pm 0.15 [*]	5.25 \pm 0.12	9.65 \pm 0.17	7.13 \pm 0.42 [*]	0.75 \pm 0.68	0.19 \pm 0.02	0.36 \pm 0.61 [*]
Group-V	1.81 \pm 0.18	4.98 \pm 0.12	2.75 \pm 0.18 ^{**}	5.31 \pm 0.15	9.31 \pm 0.14	5.63 \pm 0.09 ^{**}	0.68 \pm 0.01	0.18 \pm 0.05	0.68 \pm 0.03 ^{**}
Group-VI	1.85 \pm 0.15	4.72 \pm 0.24	2.25 \pm 0.14 ^{**}	5.54 \pm 0.25	9.71 \pm 0.28	6.21 \pm 0.18 ^{**}	0.54 \pm 0.06	0.12 \pm 0.12	0.49 \pm 0.04 ^{**}

GP1- Normal; GP2- Hyperthyroid rats; GP3- Methimazole (0.04% w/v); GP4- EEPA (100mg/kg); GP5- EEPA (200mg/kg); GP5- EEPA (400mg/kg)

All values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M (n=6). Comparisons made between ^{###}p<0.001, ^{##}p<0.01, [#]p<0.05; Normal Vs Disease control, ^{***}p<0.001, ^{**}p<0.01, ^{*}p<0.05; Disease control Vs Treatment: One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's -t test.

Graph 5: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Serum Thyroid Hormone levels (T3, T4, & TSH) in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

GP1- Normal; GP2- Hyperthyroid rats; GP3- Methimazole (0.04% w/v); GP4- EEPA (100mg/kg); GP5- EEPA (200mg/kg); GP6- EEPA (400mg/kg)

All values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M (n=6). Comparisons made between ###p<0.001, ##p<0.01, #p<0.05; Normal Vs Disease control, ***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05; Disease control Vs Treatment: One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's -t test.

Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Organ Weights

The experimental group had significantly lower thyroid gland weight than the control group. Compared to thyroxine-induced rats, control rats' thyroid and liver gland relative weights drastically decreased (P<0.01). However, these

decreases in organ weights were significantly (P<0.01) increased by treatment with Methimazole and different dosages of EEPA compared with thyroxine-induced group of rats respectively

Table 7: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Organ Weights.

Animal groups	Weight of Thyroid gland (mg)	Weight of Liver (gm)
Group-I	3.43 \pm 0.248	4.358 \pm 0.115
Group-II	2.436 \pm 0.185###	3.131 \pm 0.127###
Group-III	3.363 \pm 0.253***	4.070 \pm 0.118***
Group-IV	2.928 \pm 0.153*	3.258 \pm 0.109*
Group-V	3.095 \pm 0.284**	3.751 \pm 0.086**
Group-VI	3.290 \pm 0.154**	4.171 \pm 0.155***

Graph 6: Effect of Methimazole & EEPA on Organ weights in thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism rats

All values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M (n=6). Comparisons made between ###p<0.001, ##p<0.01, #p<0.05; Normal Vs Disease control, ***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05; Disease control Vs Treatment: One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's -t test

Histopathology thyroid glands of thyroxine induced hyperthyroid rats treated with Methimazole & EEPA. Histopathological studies were embraced to study the tissue section of the thyroid gland and liver of different experimental groups of rats. In histomorphometrically analysis, significant (P<0.01) decreases of the mean thicknesses of cross thyroid

glands and follicular lining epithelium, were detected in hyperthyroid induce with significant (P<0.01) increases of hepatocyte numbers as compared with control rats. These hyperthyroid treatments related histopathological changes of thyroid gland, was considerably inhibited by treatment of all three different dosages of EEPA extracts and Methimazole (0.04% w/v).

Fig 6.1: Histopathology of thyroid glands

CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrated the ethanolic extract of *Pimpinella anisum* was exhibited dose dependent protective effect against thyroxine induced hyperthyroidism in rats. Literature suggested that proposed mechanism involves blocking the TPO-mediated iodination of tyrosine residues in thyroglobulin, which is a crucial step in synthesizing triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4). Factors that are involved in the feedback mechanism, as well as the stimulation of hypothalamic cells to secrete thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH), may contribute to the increased levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). TSH production and release are prompted by TRH secretion into the

pituitary portal venous system and the capillaries of the pituitary gland. Irrespective of whether a person has hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism, significant thyroid damage can occur due to imbalances in thyroid hormones. Our phytochemical analysis specified flavonoids and terpenoids in EEPA; Flavonoids act as natural antithyroid compounds that can help manage hyperthyroidism by inhibiting thyroid peroxidase (TPO), reducing thyroid hormone synthesis, and inhibiting deiodinase enzyme activity. They also decrease thyroid hormone binding to transport proteins, aiding in reducing high thyroid hormone levels in the blood, though high intake may cause goiter³⁵. The antithyroid ability of EEPA might be due to the existence of flavonoids and terpenoids identified by phytochemical analysis in the present

study The promising results obtained in the present research have led to a scientific proof for the ethnopharmacological data on Pimpinella anisum fruit. Hence further studies are required for find promising bioactive molecule and targeted protein.

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